

DESIGN, CHARACTERIZATION AND IN-VITRO EVALUATION OF A NOVEL BILAYER TABLET COMBINING IMMEDIATE-RELEASE AZITHROMYCIN (WITH SUPERDISINTEGRANT VIA SLUGGING METHOD) AND SUSTAINED-RELEASE LEVOFLOXACIN (WITH HYPROMELLOSE VIA DIRECT COMPRESSION) FOR SEQUENTIAL ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY

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ABSTRACT

This study successfully developed bilayer tablets combining azithromycin (IR layer) for rapid and levofloxacin (SR layer) for rapid for prolonged release. Slugging technique and super disintegrants helped azithromycin's faster dissolution. Different grades of HPMC helped prolonged the release of Levofloxacin for up to 12 hours. Optimized bilayer tablet demonstrated good physical properties, rapid solubilization of azithromycin, and sustained release of levofloxacin.

KEYWORDS: Azithromycin, Levofloxacin, Bilayer tablets, Immediate release, Sustained release, Slugging technique, HPMC.

INTRODUCTION

Bilayer tablets are oral solid dosage forms consisting of two layers of compressed powders or granules, allowing for combination of drugs with different release profiles.^[1] The

immediate-release layer provides a quick onset of action, while the delayed-release layer provides a prolonged duration of action.^[2] They offer advantages like improved efficacy, reduced side effects, and better patient compliance.^[3]

KEYFEATURES: Immediate-Release Layer: Designed for quick onset of action, providing rapid release of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API).^[4]

Sustained-Release Layer: Designed for prolonged therapeutic effect, releasing the API gradually over time Suitable for sequential release, sustained release, and maintaining steady-state blood levels.^[5]

Applications

Therapeutic Areas: Cardiovascular disorders, diabetes, and pain management.^[3]

Antibiotics: Azithromycin and levofloxacin are used to treat bacterial infections, including respiratory tract, skin, and urinary tract infections

Azithromycin

Mechanism of Action: Inhibits bacterial protein synthesis by binding to 23S rRNA of the bacterial 50S ribosomal subunit.^[7,8]

Indications: Mild to moderate infections caused by susceptible bacteria, including respiratory, enteric, and genitourinary infections.^[6]

Side Effects: Nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, QT interval prolongation, liver toxicity, and hearing loss.^[9]

Levofloxacin

Mechanism of Action: Interferes with bacterial enzymes, DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV, essential for bacterial DNA replication.^[6]

Indications: Infections caused by susceptible bacteria, including respiratory tract, skin, and urinary tract infections.^[6]

Side Effects: Tendinitis, peripheral neuropathy, central nervous system issues, and allergic reactions.^[9]

Components of Bilayer Tablets

Immediate-Release Layer: API, excipients (diluents, binders, disintegrants, lubricants, and glidants).^[14]

Sustained-Release Layer: API, excipients (for controlled release).^[12]

Benefits

Improved patient compliance.^[3]

Enhanced therapeutic outcomes.^[13]

Reduced side effects.^[3]

Increased efficacy^[2]

NEED OF STUDY

- Levofloxacin belongs to the class of fluoroquinolone antibiotic, which is used to treat infections caused by susceptible bacteria of the upper respiratory tract, skin, urinary tract, as well as for post-exposure treatment of inhaled anthrax and the plague.
- Levofloxacin is a BCS class I drug, because it has high solubility and high permeability, dose is 500 mg once daily, half-life is 6-8 hours, bioavailability is 99%.
- Azithromycin(BCS Class II) is macrolide antibiotic used to treat certain bacterial infections, such as bronchitis, pneumonia and infections of the ears, lungs, sinuses, skin, and throat. Azithromycin also is used to treat or prevent disseminated Mycobacterium avium complex (MAC) infection.
- Azithromycin oral dose is 200mg.
- The combination of levofloxacin and Azithromycin (antibiotic) as Bilayer tablets can be designed to release the two active ingredients in a controlled manner, potentially reducing side effects and improving therapeutic outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS**List of materials****TABLE- 1: LIST OF MATERIALS.**

S. No.	MATERIALS	SOURCE
1	Azithromycin	Sain Medicaments Private Limited, Hyderabad.
2	Levofloxacin	MSN Life Sciences Private Limited, Hyderabad.
3	HPMC (K-4, K50, K-100)	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
4	Sodium starch glycolate,	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
5	Croscarmellose sodium,	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
6	Crospovidone.	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
7	Magnesium stearate,	Otto kemi
8	Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC),	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
9	DMSO	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
10	Di-sodium hydrogen ortho phosphate	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
11	Potassium dihydrogen phosphate	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited

3.3) LIST OF EQUIPMENTS TABLE:3.2 LIST OF EQUIPMENTS

S. No.	INTRUMENTS	MANUFACTURER	MODEL NO.
1	Weighing balance	Wensar Pvt. Ltd	Pgb 220
2	High shear mixer Granulator	Prism Pharma Machinery	Model: RMG 10
3	Tablet compression machine	Irm-(karnavati)enterprises Co. Pvt. Ltd	Press -idl Mt 5d+5b
4	Hardness tester	Electrolab India Pvt. Ltd.	TBH 325
5	Friability tester	Orchid	EI902
6	Dissolution tester	Lab India	Ds 8000
7	Disintegration apparatus	Electro Lab	ST-100
8	UV- spectrophotometer	PG Instruments	T60 UV
9	FTIR-spectrophotometer	Central Instrument Lab	Cary 630

Pre-Formulation studies^[62,63]

Organoleptic properties: Initial physical examination.

Procedure: Observe color, odor, taste, and appearance of the API under normal conditions.

Melting point: The melting point was determined using a capillary melting point apparatus.

Solubility studies: Solubility is determined by shake flask method. Samples were taken at specific intervals, filtered, diluted, and absorbance measured at 216 nm (azithromycin) and 302 nm (levofloxacin) to determine drug concentrations.

Determination of λ_{max} : The solution was taken to determine absorption maxima. Scanned in the region of 200-400nm.

Calibration curve of Azithromycin

- i) **Preparation of standard stock solution:** 10 mg of Azithromycin was dissolved in 10ml of DMSO from this 1 ml was taken and made upto 10 ml to give a concentration of (100 μ g/ml).
- ii) **Scanning:** From the stock solution 100 μ g/ml was prepared in DMSO and UV scan was taken between 200 to 400 nm.
- iii) **Calibration curve of Azithromycin in DMSO:** The standard solutions were prepared by proper dilutions of the primary stock solution with absolute DMSO to obtain working standards in the concentration range of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 & 60 μ g/ml of pure sample of Azithromycin.
- iv) **Preparation of sample solution:** A calibration curve for Azithromycin was plotted by measuring absorbance at 216 nm for concentrations 5-30 μ g/ml using UV-Vis

spectrophotometry.

Calibration curve of Levofloxacin

- i) Preparation of standard stock solution:** 10 mg of Levofloxacin was dissolved in 10 ml of 6.8 phosphate buffer(1000 µg/ml) , from it 1 ml was taken and made upto 10ml (100 µg/ml) with buffer .
- ii) Scanning:** From the stock solution 100µg/ml was prepared in 6.8 phosphate buffer and UV scan between 200 to 400 nm.
- iii) Calibration curve of Levofloxacin in 6.8 phosphate buffer:** Standard solutions were prepared by proper dilutions of the primary stock solution with 6.8 phosphate buffer to obtain working standards in the concentration range of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 & 30 µg/ml of pure sample of Levofloxacin.
- iv) Preparation of sample solution:** A calibration curve was plotted by measuring absorbance at 302 nm for concentrations 5-30 µg/ml using UV-Vis spectrophotometry.

Determination of drug polymer compatibility studies using FTIR

FTIR spectroscopy was used to study drug-excipient interactions using the KBr pellet method, recording the spectrum to assess physical and chemical stability.

Drug – excipient compatibility study

FTIR analysis showed no physical or chemical interactions between the drug and excipients, confirming their compatibility for matrix tablet preparation.

FORMULATION AND DEVELOPMENT

Formulation development of Azithromycin as immediate release

The immediate release ingredients were accurately weighed and added into the blender in ascending order. The powder mix was blended for 20 minutes to obtain uniform distribution of the drug in formulation and subjected for preformulation studies. All the formulation components were passed through sieve #60, weighed, mixed, and compressed into tablet using 14 mm punch on Rotary tablet minipress-I.

A1–A3 evaluate CCS, SSG, and CP in direct compression. A4–A6 use the same super disintegrants but apply slugging to assess whether particle size modification improves flow, compressibility, content uniformity, and dissolution of a poorly compressible API like azithromycin.

Procedure

- Manufacturing procedure (concise SOPs)
- Direct compression (A1, A2 & A3)

Mixed all components (API, MCC, disintegrant, Mg stearate).

Weight accurately 300mg for a tablets

Compress with 8–10 mm flat/bevel punches; adjust target hardness ~4–6 kp.

- Slugging Technique (A4, A5 & A6)

Mixing API + MCC + selected super disintegrant.

Pre-compress into slugs at higher pressure (no lubricant) to form compacted ribbons/tablets.

Mill slugs to desired granule size; re-sift.

Blend granules with Mg. stearate .

Final compression to 300 mg tablets at similar hardness target.

Table 3.5- Formulation development of azithromycin as immediate release layer.

Ingredients (mg)	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6
Azithromycin	200	200	200	200	200	200
MCC	83	83	83	83	83	83
Croscarmellose sodium	15	0	0	15	0	0
Sodium starch glycolate	0	15	0	0	15	0
Crospovidone	0	0	15	0	0	15
Magnesium Stearate	2	2	2	2	2	2
Total weight	300	300	300	300	300	300

1) Formulation development of Levofloxacin as sustained release

The sustained release ingredients were weighed and added into the blender. The powder mix was blended for 20 min. to obtain uniform distribution of the drug in formulation and subjected for pre-formulation studies. Tablets were prepared by direct compression method with 14 mm stainless steel punch using rotary press.

Compression force for all the tablets was adjusted to get tablets of hardness 5-8 kg/cm².

Table no. 3.6:- Formulation design of Levofloxacin sustained release.

Ingredients	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8	L9
Levofloxacin	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500
MCC	76	76	76	36	36	36	116	116	116
HPMC K-4	200	0	0	240	0	0	160	0	0
HMPC K-15	0	200	0	0	240	0	0	160	0
HPMCK-100	0	0	200	0	0	240	0	0	160
Magnesium Stearate	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Colouring agent	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Total weight	800	800	800	800	800	800	800	800	800

A5 batch from Azithromycin immediate release layer and L7 batch from Levofloxacin sustained release layer were selected to form Optimized bilayer tablet. Composition of bilayer tablet was shown in table no.7

Bilayer tablets were prepared using a Rotary tablet minipress-I, with the sustained release layer compressed first, followed by the immediate release layer, using a 14 mm circular punch.

TABLET CHARACTERIZATION.^[64,65]

Flow Properties

Angle of repose= $\tan^{-1} (h/r)$ Where, h = height of a pile (2 cm) r = radius of pile base.

Bulk density:- Bulk density was determined by pouring blend into a graduated cylinder. The bulk volume and weight of the powder was determined.

Bulk density=Weight of sample in gram/ volume occupied by the sample

Tapped density

Tapped density= Wt. of sample in gram/Tapped volume

Compressibility Index or Carr's Index

Carr's index is measured using the values of bulk density and tapped density.

% Compressibility = $\frac{\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density}}{\text{Tapped density}} \times 100$

Hausner's ratio: It indicates the flow properties of the powder and ratio of tapped density to the bulk density of the powder or granules.

Hausner ratio= tapped density/ bulk density

Formulation of optimize bilayer tablet of Azithromycin immediate release layer and

Levofloxacin sustained release layer.

Table 3.7- Formulation of optimize bilayer tablet of Azithromycin immediate release layer and Levofloxacin sustained release layer.

S. No.	Formulation of Azithromycin Immediate release Layer (A5)		Formulation of Levofloxacin sustained release Layer (L7)	
	Ingredients	Formulation	Ingredients	Formulation
1	Azithromycin	200	Levofloxacin	500
2	Micro crystalline cellulose	83	Micro crystalline cellulose	116
3	Sodium starch glycolate	15	Colouring agent	12
4	Magnesium stearate	2	Magnesium stearate	12
5			HPMC K-4	160
	Total Weight	300	Total Weight	800

Preparation of Azithromycin and levofloxacin bilayer tablet.

EVALUATION OF TABLETS^[66,67]

Post compression parameters

Thickness and diameter: Thickness of tablet is important for uniformity of tablet size. Thickness was measured using vernier calliper. It was determined by checking ten tablets from each batch.

Hardness test: The resistance of tablets to breakage, under conditions of storage, transportation or handling before usage depends on its hardness. The hardness of tablet was measured by Monsanto hardness tester. Ten tablets from the batch were used for hardness studies and results are expressed in Kg/cm².

Weight variation test: Ten tablets were selected at random, individually weighed in a single pan electronic balance and the average weight was calculated.

Table 3.8- Average weight of tablet according to I.P specification.

S.No.	Average weight of tablet	Percentage
1	80 mg or less	± 10%
2	More than 80mg and less than 250mg	± 7.5%
3	250 mg or more	± 5%

Friability: This test is performed to evaluate the ability of tablets to withstand abrasion in packing, handling and transporting. Initial weight of 20 tablets is taken and these are placed in the friabilator, rotating at 25 rpm for 4min. The difference in the weight is noted and expressed a percentage. It should be preferably between 0.5 to 1.0%. **%friability = (W1-W2)/W1 X 100** Where, **W1= weight of tablets before test W2 = weight of tablets after test**

Disintegration test: For a drug to be absorbed from a solid dosage form after oral administration, it must be in solution, and the first important step toward this condition is usually the break-up of the tablet; a process known as disintegration. The disintegration test is a measure of the time required under a given set of conditions for a group of tablets to disintegrate into particles which will pass through a 10 mesh screen. Generally, the test is useful as a quality assurance tool for conventional dosage forms.

Disintegration time: Uncoated tablet for immediate release: 5-30 minutes.

Uncoated tablet for sustained release: 8-12 hrs

In vitro Dissolution Studies for immediate release layer of Azithromycin &

Levofloxacin: The samples withdrawn were filtered through 0.45µ membrane filter, and drug release in each sample was analyzed after suitable dilution by UV Spectrophotometer at 216nm.

Dissolution Conditions

Medium	: pH 6.8 phosphate buffer
Type of Apparatus	: USP –II (paddle type) RPM 75
Volume	: 900 mL
Run time	: 1hour
Temperature	: 37± 0.5°C

In vitro dissolution studies for sustained release layer of Levofloxacin: 6.8 phosphate buffer was used as a dissolution medium 5ml of sample was withdrawn at predetermined time intervals replacing with an equal quantity of drug free dissolution fluid. The samples withdrawn were filtered through 0.45 μ membrane filter, and drug release in each sample was analyzed after suitable dilution by UV Spectrophotometer at 302nm.

Dissolution Conditions

Same previous

Run time : 12 hour.

Time intervals : 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10, 11, 12 hrs

Kinetic Studies: The following plots were made: cumulative % drug release vs time (zero order kinetic model); log cumulative of % drug remaining vs time (first order kinetic model); cumulative % drug release vs square root of time (Higuchi model); : cumulative % drug release vs time (Peppas model). The regression coefficient R^2 value nearer to 1 indicates the model best fits the release mechanism.

Stability studies: The formulation A5 & L1 was selected and the stability studies were carried out at 25 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C, 60 \pm 5% RH (Long term stability condition), 30 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C, 65 \pm 5% RH (intermediate condition) and 40 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C, 75 \pm 5 $^{\circ}$ C (accelerated conditions), the tablets were packed in amber colour screwcap container and kept in above said condition for period of six months. The tablets were analyzed periodically for their physical appearance and in-vitro drug release.

Dissolution studies of Azithromycin and Levofloxacin from bilayer tablet

The dissolution studies of optimized Azithromycin and Levofloxacin bilayer tablet was studied by conducting dissolution using USP Type II dissolution apparatus.

Tablets were placed in 900ml of buffer at 37 \pm 0.5 $^{\circ}$ C at 75 rpm for 1 hour and then changed to 900ml of 6.8 phosphate buffer at 37 \pm 0.5 $^{\circ}$ C at 50 rpm. 5ml of sample were withdrawn at the intervals of every 10 min initially for one hour in 6.8 phosphate buffer samples were withdrawn every 1 hour. Sampling was carried out and every time replaced with fresh 5ml of buffer. The absorbance of solution was recorded at 216 nm for Azithromycin and 302 nm for Levofloxacin using buffer as blank. The result was calculated as Percentage drug release of Azithromycin and Levofloxacin.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Organoleptic Properties of Azithromycin & Levofloxacin

S. No.	Organoleptic Properties of Azithromycin		Organoleptic Properties of Levofloxacin	
	Parameters	Drug	Parameters	Drug
1	Colour	white to off-white	Colour	light-yellowish-white to yellow-white crystal
2	Odour	Odourless	Odour	Odourless
3	Taste	Metallic	Taste	Slightly Bitter
4	Appearance	Fine crystalline	Appearance	Crystalline powder
5	State	Solid	State	Solid

a. Melting point

Table 4.2: Melting point determination of Azithromycin & Levofloxacin.

Drug	Reported melting point	Observed melting point
Azithromycin	225-227°C	226°C
Levofloxacin	113-115°C	113°C

Solubility of Azithromycin & Levofloxacin in various solvents.

Solvent	Solubility of Azithromycin	Solubility of Levofloxacin
Water	0.8 mg/ml	5 mg/ml
Methanol	12	1-4
0.1 N HCL	1-2	44.5
6.8 pH phosphate buffer	14	52
Ethanol	23	26
DMSO	33	31

Determination of drug absorbance

Fig- 4.1: Determination of λ max of Azithromycin.

Solution of Azithromycin concentration of 10 μ g/ml was scanned in the range of wavelength 200-400 nm. The absorption spectrum was found wavelength of 216 nm in phosphate buffer pH 6.8.

Fig-4.2: Determination of λ max of Levofloxacin in phosphate buffer 6.8.

Solution of Levofloxacin concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was scanned in the range of wavelength 200-400 nm. The absorption spectrum was found wavelength of 302nm in phosphate buffer pH 6.8.

Calibration curve

Table 4.4 & 4.5: CALIBRATION CURVE DATA OF AZITHROMYCIN & LEVOFLOXACIN IN 6.8 pH PHOSPHATE BUFFER.

Observation:- R^2 value of Azithromycin was found to be 0.9989 & it obeys beer's lambert's law in concentration range of 10-60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Observation:- R² value of Levofloxacin was found to be 0.9993 and indicate that it obeys beer’s lambert’s law in concentration range of 10-60 µg/ml.

4.4.1- Drug compatibility for Azithromycin by FTIR Spectroscopy

Fig-4.5: FTIR spectra of Azithromycin pure drug.

Fig-4.6: FTIR spectra of Azithromycin + excipient.

4.4.2-Drug compatibility for Levofloxacin by FTIR Spectroscopy

Fig-4.7: FTIR spectra of Levofloxacin pure drug.

Fig-4.8: FTIR spectra of Levofloxacin + excipient.

EVALUATION OF PRE & POST COMPRESSION PARAMETERS FOR AZITHROMYCIN AND LEVOFLOXACIN

Evaluation parameters of powder blend for azithromycin (immediate release layer) & levofloxacin(sustained release layers)

The powder blends for immediate release and sustained release layers showed satisfactory flow behaviour based on bulk density values, ensuring uniform tablet weight and content uniformity.

Evaluation of optimized bilayer tablet of azithromycin immediate release and levofloxacin sustained release

Optimized bilayer tablet was prepared from optimized formulation of azithromycin immediate release Layer (A5) & levofloxacin sustained release Layer (L7).

Evaluation of post compression parameters of Bilayer Tablet

All the formulations were subjected for post compression evaluation such as bulk density, tapped density, Hausner's ratio and Carr's index. All the prepared bilayer tablets were subjected to compendial test for post compression evaluation.

PRECOMPRESSION EVALUATION OF AZITHROMYCIN

Table 4.5- Results of precompression evaluation of azithromycin immediate release layer.

Formulations	Angle of Repose (θ)	Loose bulk density g/ml	Tapped density (g/ml)	%Compressibility
A1	24.7 \pm 0.41	0.425 \pm 0.03	0.512 \pm 0.017	16.99
A2	28.6 \pm 0.52	0.427 \pm 0.07	0.551 \pm 0.019	22.5
A3	26.5 \pm 0.48	0.433 \pm 0.11	0.532 \pm 0.021	18.6
A4	27.7 \pm 0.71	0.429 \pm 0.09	0.529 \pm 0.24	18.90
A5	25.5 \pm 0.37	0.432 \pm 0.08	0.517 \pm 0.27	16.44
A6	27.4 \pm 0.46	0.431 \pm 0.12	0.530 \pm 0.22	18.67

POST COMPRESSION EVALUATION OF AZITHROMYCIN TABLET

Table 4.6- Results of post compression evaluation of azithromycin immediate release layer.

Formulation	Average Weight (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Hardness Kg/cm ²	Friability (%)	Disintegration Time (seconds)	Drug Content (%)
A1	300.12 \pm 0.06	3.7 \pm 0.11	5.18	0.16	31	89.25 \pm 0.26
A2	299.01 \pm 0.25	3.8 \pm 0.15	5.09	0.20	29	94.24 \pm 0.11
A3	298.24 \pm 0.48	3.6 \pm 0.09	5.17	0.14	28	92.28 \pm 0.24
A4	301.02 \pm 0.26	3.7 \pm 0.04	5.24	0.18	26	95.27 \pm 0.51
A5	300.14 \pm 0.15	3.8 \pm 0.06	5.25	0.15	26	98.26 \pm 0.49
A6	302.78 \pm 0.02	3.7 \pm 0.03	5.14	0.19	27	97.78 \pm 0.12

PRECOMPRESSION EVALUATION OF LEVOFLOXACIN TABLETS

Table 4.7- Results of precompression evaluation of levofloxacin

Formulations	Angle of Repose (θ)	Loose bulk density (g/ml)	Tapped density (g/ml)	%Compressibility
L1	27 ⁰ 53 \pm 0.36	0.373 \pm 0.017	0.432 \pm 0.022	12.15
L2	25 ⁰ 57 \pm 0.24	0.380 \pm 0.023	0.436 \pm 0.017	12.84
L3	24 ⁰ 31 \pm 0.23	0.364 \pm 0.032	0.423 \pm 0.024	13.94
L4	24 ⁰ 41 \pm 0.28	0.377 \pm 0.018	0.436 \pm 0.028	13.53

L5	25 ⁰ 42±0.25	0.376±0.024	0.427±0.023	11.94
L6	26042±0.26	0.377±0.028	0.434±0.027	13.13
L7	24⁰21±0.21	0.371±0.030	0.421±0.025	11.87
L8	25 ⁰ 27±0.31	0.375±0.023	0.432±0.023	13.19
L9	26 ⁰ 19±0.27	0.370±0.028	0.429±0.026	13.75

POST COMPRESSION EVALUATION OF LEVOFLOXACIN TABLET

Table 4.8- Results of post compression evaluation of levofloxacin sustained release layer.

Formulations	Average Weight (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Hardness	Friability (%)	Drug Content (%)
L1	699.21±0.15	5.2	6.6	0.85±0.29	99.21±0.25
L2	703.15±0.2	5.2	6.2	0.63±0.12	97.35±0.92
L3	695.02±0.41	5.3	6.3	0.53±0.10	98.73±0.37
L4	701.11±0.27	5.3	6.4	0.69±0.87	92.46±0.47
L5	698.24±0.26	5.7	6.7	0.67±0.19	95.71±0.19
L6	696.06±0.14	5.2	7.2	0.54±0.26	96.87±0.22
L7	699.89±0.18	5.4	7.5	0.72±0.19	99.51±0.23
L8	694.40±0.14	5.1	7.1	0.51±0.66	98.11±0.40
L9	697.77±0.23	5.5	7.5	0.72±0.19	97.38±0.23

IN-VITRO DISSOLUTION STUDY OF AZITHROMYCIN & LEVOFLOXACIN BILAYER TABLETS

Table 4.9- In vitro dissolution study of azithromycin Cumulative percent drug release.

Time (Min)	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	Azimax 200 mg
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	10.2±0.21	7.8±0.23	17.1±0.34	20.1±0.42	22.15±0.8	20.6±0.24	18±0.04
10	19.4±0.32	16.11±0.33	30.2±0.45	35.8±0.53	68.4±0.50	45.4±0.53	29.±0.45
15	28.1±0.43	29.14±0.35	47.26±0.63	50.6±0.65	84.7±0.32	70.1±0.61	36.08±0.5
20	33.4±0.54	42.9±0.56	63.8±0.82	76.5±0.79	98.2±0.41	86.4±0.74	74.4±0.5
25	40.6±0.65	57.6±0.67	71.5±0.93	89.2±0.83	100.2±0.41	99.8±0.9	88±0.6
30	62.7±0.6	73.8±0.69	81.1±0.33	100.8±0.94	100.2±0.41	100±0.9	100±0.8

Fig-4.9: In vitro dissolution studies of azithromycin formulations.

Table 4.10- In vitro dissolution study of levofloxacin.

Time	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8	L9	Levaquin
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	7.19	6.64	6.96	7.13	6.02	6.32	8.96	7.99	7.43	9.04
1	14.46	12.96	11.89	12.11	11.21	11.06	15.14	13.49	12.12	15.2
2	24.25	19.14	17.12	22.58	18.98	16.36	28.92	20.16	19.26	29.0
3	33.58	27.98	25.03	31.12	28.80	23.56	37.67	29.58	27.73	38.47
4	41.42	37.46	32.86	40.14	34.70	31.67	47.12	40.14	39.01	46.77
6	59.48	52.45	41.46	56.28	50.42	40.44	59.49	54.92	52.96	61.08
8	65.26	62.79	60.99	61.01	60.34	59.54	68.54	66.12	66.14	66.2
10	71.62	72.56	73.14	74.43	71.47	70.26	79.58	76.65	77.99	81.36
11	82.16	80.45	80.90	80.52	79.69	78.12	88.42	85.75	83.37	89.34
12	97.77	94.57	91.17	92.26	91.73	90.06	99.61	95.08	93.35	100.0

Fig- 4.10: In-vitro diffusion studies of Sustained Release levofloxacin formulation(L1-L9)**Table 4.11: In-vitro Dissolution profile of optimized bilayer tablets in 6.8 PO4 buffer.**

S. No.	Sampling time	Percentage(%) drug released Azithromycin	Percentage(%) drug released levofloxacin
1	15 mins	84.7±	4.21
2	30 mins	100.2±	8.90
3	1 hr	-	15.14
4	2 hr	-	28.92
6	3 hr	-	37.67
7	4 hr	-	47.12
8	6 hr	-	59.49
9	8 hr	-	68.54
10	10 hr	-	79.58
11	11 hr	-	88.42
12	12 hr	-	99.61

Fig-4.12: In vitro Dissolution profile of optimized bilayer tablets.

KINETIC STUDIES

Table 4.12- kinetic studies of optimised levofloxacin formulation.

PARAMETERS	ZERO ORDER	FIRST ORDER	HIGUCHI	PEPPAS
	% CDR Vs T	Log % Remain Vs T	%CDR Vs \sqrt{T}	Log C Vs Log T
Slope	7.4966	-0.1219	31.16	0.731
Intercept	9.3084	2.977	15.479	1.1998
Correlation	0.98726	0.84191	0.995138	0.996945
R ²	0.9747	0.7089	0.9939	0.9903

Fig-4.14: First order release graph for L7 sustained release formulation

Fig-4.13: Zero order release graph for L7 sustained release formulation.

Fig-4.15: Higuchi model graph for L7 sustained release formulation.

Fig-4.16: Peppas model for L7 sustained release formulation.

The best correlation coefficient value (0.9939) indicates the best release mechanism (Release kinetics).

STABILITY STUDIES

Results of stability studies are shown in table. Physical appearances of all formulations did not show any significant changes.

Table 4.13- Stability studies of optimized formulation.

		25±2 ⁰ C,60±5%RH	30 ±2 ⁰ C,65±5 ⁰ C %RH	40±2 ⁰ C,75±5%RH							
Drug	Time (hr)	Initial	1st Month	3rd Month	6th Month	1st Month	3rd Month	6th Month	1st Month	3rd Month	6th Month
Azithromycin	15 mins	84.7	84.7	84.3	84.2	83.9	82.8	82.7	84.0	83.4	82.9
	30 mins	100.2	100.2	100.1	100.0	99.8	99.7	99.6	100.0	99.5	98.8
Levofloxacin	1	14.22	14.22	14.18	14.14	13.9	13.8	13.7	14.2	13.5	12.7
	2	21.03	21.03	20.99	20.97	19.5	19.4	19.3	20.3	19.7	18.8
	3	31.22	31.22	31.18	31.16	29.3	29.2	29.1	30.1	29.7	28.7
	4	40.78	40.78	40.75	40.73	39.9	39.8	39.7	40.2	39.6	38.8
	6	63.01	63.01	62.98	62.96	61.4	61.3	61.2	62.2	61.3	60.1
	8	81.80	81.80	81.76	81.74	79.4	79.4	79.3	80.1	79.5	78.7
	10	92.93	92.93	92.89	92.86	90.2	90.1	90.0	91.0	92.9	91.8
	12	99.44	99.44	99.41	99.38	99.40	98.3	98.2	99.2	98.47	97.51

DISCUSSION

All the Stability studies are within the limits.

CONCLUSION

The study found that azithromycin and levofloxacin had better solubility in 6.8 phosphate buffer, with no interaction between drugs and excipients. The optimized formulations showed satisfactory physical properties, with azithromycin achieving 100% release within 30 minutes and levofloxacin sustaining release for 12 hours. Stability studies confirmed the drugs' stability at various temperatures and humidity conditions.

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